

EVALUATION OF ASPHALT PAVEMENT MARSHALL PROPERTIES USING RECLAIMED ASPHALT IN COLD MIX TECHNOLOGY FOR WEARING COURSE

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14020377

ABSTRACT

The current challenge by global warming and the need to reduce carbon dioxide emissions has led to a great shift for many industries to cold mix asphalt (CMA) which has been increasingly recognized as an important alternative worldwide. When recycled asphalt pavement (RAP) is introduced in the mix, cold-mix recycled asphalt Pavement (CRAP) is obtained, which is known for cost effectiveness and environmental friendliness because of its huge saving in cost of material and reduced greenhouse gas emission (GHG). CRAP has been in use for different purposes for roads. In this project, medium set cationic emulsion (5%-11%), cement (0-6%), RAP (0-95%), lime (0-0.2%), aggregates were used as materials. The research was aimed at the evaluation of the marshall properties of CRAP. Marshall asphalt institute method was used to establish the optimum emulsion content using different percentages of mixture compositions. The optimum values of emulsion content and lime was found to be 8% and 0.1% respectively. Similarly, it was discovered that specimens containing 3% of cement as filler satisfactorily performed with 20% of RAP, those that contained 5% of cement as filler satisfactorily performed with up to 70% of RAP, while those specimens that contained 6% of cement as filler satisfactorily performed with up to 95% of RAP.

Keywords: Cold-Mix, Recycled asphalt, Pavement

INTRODUCTION

Cold mix asphalt (CMA) technology is one of the most sustainable technology (green) available for the construction of flexible pavement to date, because of the lower production temperatures involved. The mechanical properties of the designed CMA depend on the mixing of aggregates, prewetting water content, emulsion, curing time, and pulse repetition periods for determination of resilient modulus (Meena *et al.*, 2023). Cold mix asphalt (CMA) has been increasingly recognized as an important alternative worldwide. One of the common types of CMA is cold bitumen emulsion mixture (CBEM) (Nassar *et al.*, 2016)). Sustainable road construction practice is founded on four pillars: (a) satisfactory performance of pavement during its design life, (b) environment-friendly technology, (c) wise utilization of money and (d) construction should be favorable to human safety, health, and comfort (Sharma *et al.*, 2020). One way to construct environmentally sound roads is through the use of recycled asphalt pavement (RAP) materials. When recycled asphalt pavement (RAP) is introduced in the mix, cold-mix recycled asphalt Pavement (CRAP) is obtained, which is known for cost effectiveness and environmental friendliness because of its huge saving in cost of material and reduced green house gas emission (GHG). CRAP has been in use for different purposes that includes sub base course and base course materials for roads. In this project emulsion, cement, RAP, lime, aggregates were used as materials to produce cold-mix

recycled asphalt pavement for use in wearing course for the road. Although cold mix asphalt (CMA) has several advantages over hot mix asphalt (HMA) in terms of safety in manufacturing and application, fuel saving, non-emission of harmful gases and ease in laying of the paving mix in any climatic condition, it has attracted little attention, this is not unconnected with its downside of having high air void content, weak early strength gain, and longtime for curing because of emulsion, which means CMA requires more compaction on site to reduce the air void content. Research and field application of CMA has not been enough compared to the HMA. Advancement of sustainable/green technology like cold mix technology should be given emphasis in view of environmental requirements (Dash *et al.*, 2022).

The methods of rehabilitation and strengthening of the road network using hot mixtures currently being used are conservative, methods of total reconstruction and overlays which are very costly, time consuming and non-eco-efficient. Eco-friendliness, energy efficiency and cost effectiveness are major drivers responsible for cold recycled asphalt mixtures being considered as alternatives to hot mixtures (Oke, 2011). Fundamentally, problems with cold mix asphalt includes high air void content, weak early strength gain, and longtime for curing because of emulsion.

Approximately 6 liters of fuel are used for drying and heating one ton of aggregates (Thakur *et al.*, 2015), which would expand to enormously huge quantities considering

lots of tons of aggregates that are used for road construction every year. This implies that the hot mix asphalt cement becomes the most energy consuming. One of the most significant benefits of Cold mix is the drastic decrease in energy use. Young (2007) has approximated that for every 6 °C reduction in temperature, fuel consumption is reduced by 2–3 %. In the developed countries of the world especially those that have temperate climates like France, U.S.A, and Sweden, RAP and emulsified bitumen are being used as the binding medium for surface treatment works, and they have since worked thoroughly for the production and use of cold mixtures in road Construction. However, evidence from the literature indicates that little has been done to ascertain the performance and suitability of cold mix materials in developing countries located in hot tropical climates such as Nigeria, Ghana, Benin, Burkina Faso, Republic of Congo, among others. This research is aimed at evaluating the Marshall properties of cold mix recycled asphalt pavement (CRAP).

Previous researchers like, Usman *et al.*, (2021), Algraiti and Kavussi (2023), Al-Sabaei *et al.* (2023), Flores *et al.* (2020), Buchler *et al.* (2018) and Filho *et al.* (2020), all worked on similar area, on the asphalt pavement mixtures, though some have either used hot mix, super pave gyratory method of compaction, worked on sub base layer of the road, base layer of the road, or used rejuvenator, some did not use RAP at all, but the difference of this research with their own is working on cold-mix recycled asphalt pavement for wearing course layer of the road, applying marshall method of compaction.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Materials

The recycle asphalt Pavement (RAP) material, 30 years of age was sourced from Julius Berger construction site yard

Table 1: Physical Properties of Aggregates

S/N	Test Done	Unit	ASTM Method	Results	Specifications	Remark
1	Aggregate crushing Value (CV)	%	ASTM C 535	23.7	< 30	OK
2	Aggregate Impact Value (IV)	%	ASTM D 5874	26.0	< 30	OK
3	Elongation Index (EI)	%	ASTM D 4791	17.32	< 20	OK
4	Flakiness Index (FI)	%	ASTM D 4791	21.14	< 25	OK
5	Specific gravity of Coarse aggregates	g/cm ³	ASTM C 127	2.73	2.55-2.95	OK
6	Specific gravity of Fine aggregates	g/cm ³	ASTM C 127	2.65	2.55-2.95	OK
7	Loss angeles Abrasion Value (LAAV)	%	ASTM C 535	23.4	< 40	OK
8	Water Absorption (ABS)	%	ASTM C 1585	0.54	2% Max	OK
9	Sand Equivalency/clay content	%	ASTM C 142	15.3	45% min	OK

Table 2: Physical Properties of RAP

S/N	Test Done	Unit	ASTM Method	Results	Specifications	Remark
1	Aggregate crushing Value (CV)	%	ASTM C 535	22.5	< 30	OK
2	Aggregate Impact Value (IV)	%	ASTM D 5874	24.2	< 30	OK
3	Elongation Index (EI)	%	ASTM D 4791	12.13	< 20	OK
4	Flakiness Index (FI)	%	ASTM D 4791	17.00	< 25	OK
5	Specific gravity of Coarse aggregates	g/cm ³	ASTM C 127	2.71	2.55-2.95	OK
6	Specific gravity of Fine aggregates	g/cm ³	ASTM C 127	2.62	2.55-2.95	OK
7	Water Absorption (ABS)	%	ASTM C 1585	0.34	2% Max	OK

No-002 located along Kaduna-Zaria Road, its physical properties is shown in Table 2 and its gradation is shown in Table 4. Aggregates was sourced from samaru quarry granite site at Zaria located opposite school of aviation, its physical properties is shown in Table 1 and its gradation is shown in Table 3. Cationic medium set emulsion was sourced from Katsina emulsion plant, Katsina state and its physical properties is shown in Table 6. Lime and OPC-42.5N-cement were sourced from an open market. The chemical composition of lime is shown in Table 5. Table 1 showed that the aggregates passed the required specifications as compared with the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM).

Table 2 showed that the recycled asphalt pavement materials (RAP) passed the required specifications as compared with the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM).

Plate 1: Materials Involved in the Research

Table 3 showed that the gradation of the fresh aggregates used in the mix passed the required specifications as

Table 3: Gradation for the Job Mix (Fresh Aggregates)

S/N	Sieve Nos	Cumulative % passing(%)	FMWH Specification for Wearing Course	Remarks
1	12.5mm	99.64	85-100	Ok
2	9.5mm	77.80	75-92	Ok
3	6.4mm	80.60	65-82	Ok
4	2.8mm	63.20	50-65	Ok
5	1.25mm	50.80	36-51	Ok
6	600µm	37.90	26-40	Ok
7	300µm	23.60	18-30	Ok
8	150µm	20.50	13-24	Ok
9	75µm	7.30	7-14	Ok

compared with the Federal Ministry of Works and Housing (FMWH) specifications.

with the European Standards (EN) and American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM).

Table 4: Gradation For the RAP Aggregates.

S/N	Sieve Nos	Cumulative % passing (%)	FMWH Specification for Binder Course	Remarks
1	12.5mm	78.3	55-80	Ok
2	9.5mm	69.3	47-70	Ok
3	6.4mm	58.6	40-60	Ok
4	2.8mm	41.4	27-45	Ok
5	1.25mm	28.3	20-34	Ok
6	600µm	18.5	14-27	Ok
7	300µm	10.5	8-20	Ok
8	150µm	5.5	5-15	Ok
9	75µm	1.9	2-7	Ok

Table 4 showed that the gradation of the recycled asphalt pavement materials (RAP) used in the mix passed the required specifications as compared with the Federal Ministry of Works and Housing specifications (FMWH).

Table 5 showed that the lime chemical composition has very high Calcium Oxide content (87.597%) which is responsible for high value of stability when used in the mix.

Table 6 showed that all the tests carried out on Cationic emulsion passed the required specifications as compared

Table 6: Physical Properties of Cationic Emulsion

Property	Test results	Testing standards	Code
Color	Black to dark brown in a liquid state		
Particle charge	Positive	Positive	EN 1430
Viscosity at 25 °C (sec.)	118	30-150	EN 13614
Penetration, (dmms)	66	60-70	EN 1428
Bulk Density (g/cm ³)	1.014	0.97-1.02	ASTM D2726
Bitumen content	50%	40-80%	EN 1428

Methods

Laboratory Sampling Preparation and mix design

Marshall's design mix approach was used as stated in ASTM D6927 for the design method to evaluate compacted specimen samples. The sample specimens were prepared using standard method of mixing, and

Plate 2: (a) Prepared Test Samples and (b) Automated Compaction Machine

Figure 1: Overall Research Methodology

Table 5: Chemical Composition of Lime (Ca(OH)₂)

S/N	layer	Component	Type	concentration	Error	Units	Mole (%)	Error
1	1	SiO ₂	Calc	0.527	0.211	Wt.%	0.486	0.195
2	1	V ₂ O ₅	Calc	0.07	0.022	Wt.%	0.021	0.007
3	1	Cr ₂ O ₃	Calc	0	0	Wt.%	0	0
4	1	MnO	Calc	0.011	0.009	Wt.%	0.009	0.007
5	1	Fe ₂ O ₃	Calc	0.188	0.017	Wt.%	0.065	0.006
6	1	Co ₃ O ₄	Calc	0.072	0.01	Wt.%	0.016	0.002
7	1	NiO	Calc	0.02	0.005	Wt.%	0.015	0.004
8	1	CuO	Calc	0.063	0.009	Wt.%	0.044	0.006
9	1	Nb ₂ O ₃	Calc	0.103	0.352	Wt.%	0.025	0.083
10	1	MoO ₃	Calc	0	0	Wt.%	0	0
11	1	WO ₃	Calc	0.069	0.043	Wt.%	0.016	0.01
12	1	P ₂ O ₅	Calc	0	0	Wt.%	0	0
13	1	SO ₃	Calc	0.207	0.068	Wt.%	0.143	0.047
14	1	CaO	Calc	87.597	0.483	Wt.%	86.546	0.477
15	1	MgO	Calc	7.526	6.705	Wt.%	10.346	9.218
16	1	K ₂ O	Calc	0	0	Wt.%	0	0
17	1	BaO	Calc	0.073	0.067	Wt.%	0.026	0.024
18	1	Al ₂ O ₃	Calc	2.35	1.081	Wt.%	1.277	0.588
19	1	Ta ₂ O ₅	Calc	0.065	0.036	Wt.%	0.008	0.005
20	1	TiO ₂	Calc	0	0	Wt.%	0	0
21	1	ZnO	Calc	0.018	0.008	Wt.%	0.012	0.005
22	1	Ag ₂ O	Calc	0	0	Wt.%	0	0
23	1	Cl	Calc	0.462	0.036	Wt.%	0.722	0.056
24	1	ZrO ₂	Calc	0.104	0.092	Wt.%	0.047	0.041
25	1	SnO ₂	Calc	0.474	1.175	Wt.%	0.174	0.432

compaction. The asphalt mixture was compacted with 75 blows back and front using the Marshall automated compactor machine. After the compaction, the samples' diameter and thickness are approximately 100mm and 70 mm, respectively. Samples were adequately positioned on a leveled and smooth surface at ambient temperature overnight before subsequent testing to determine the optimum bitumen content (OBC) and other mechanical performance tests.

A total of 105-number samples using marshal method were prepared containing different combinations and with three specimens for each, the average value was observed and recorded for each, marshal and volumetric analysis were carried out and their respective bulk densities, total void in the mix (AV), total void in mineral aggregates (VMA), Void filled by bitumen (VFB), stability (s), and flow (f) where established. The asphalt samples were placed in a

water bath for 40 minutes at 60°C before testing for stability and flow.

Legend

- i. Filler-3+2 Cem -D means 3% of cement and 2% of granite dust was used as filler using Zero additive.
- ii. Filler-5 Cem means 5% of cement was used as filler using Zero additive.
- iii. Filler-6 Cem means 6% of cement was used as filler using Zero additive.
- iv. Filler-7 Cem means 7% of cement was used as filler using Zero additive.
- v. Filler-3+2 Cem -D -Lm means 3% of cement and 2% of granite dust was used as filler using Lime as additive.
- vi. Filler-5 Cem- Lm means 5% of cement was used as filler using Lime as additive.
- vii. Filler-6 CEM Lm means 6% of cement was used as filler using Lime as additive.

Research Methodology

See (Figure 1).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 represents plots of stability vs. emulsion content

using different percentages of cements and granites dust in filler. It is observed that the optimum value of stability is at 8% emulsion content. As the percentage of cement increases in filler, the value of stability increases this is because of the high content of calcium oxide in cement which contributes to the strength.

Figure 4 represents plots of total voids in the mix vs emulsion content using different percentages of cements and granites dust in filler. It is observed that as the percentage of emulsion content increases the total voids in the mix reduces. This is because the emulsion particles keep filling the voids in the mix which makes it stronger and more durable. Similar pattern was observed in research conducted by Dash and Panda (2018).

Figure 5 represents plots of voids filled by bitumen in the mix vs emulsion content using different percentages of cements and granites dust in filler. It is shown that as the percentage of emulsion content increases the voids filled by bitumen increases. This is because the emulsion particles keep filling the voids in the mix which makes it stronger

Figure 2: Plot of Stability vs. Emulsion Content

Figure 3: Plot of Bulk Density vs. Emulsion Content

Figure 4: Plot of Total Void in the Mix (AV) vs. Emulsion Content

Figure 5: Plot of Void Filled by Asphalt (VFA) vs. Emulsion Content

Figure 6: Plot of Flow vs. Emulsion Content

and more durable. Similar trend was observed in a research conducted by Dash and Panda (2018).

Figure 6 represents plots of flow vs emulsion content using different percentages of cements and granites dust in filler.

Table 7: Marshall and Volumetric Properties of Asphaltic Samples Containing RAP

	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Response 1	Response 2	Response 3	Response 4	Response 5	Response 6
Run	Filler	Lime (re-agent)	RAP	BSG	AV	VMA	VFB	S	F
	Factor-1 emulsion at 8%								
	Cement+Dust								
1	3+2	0.1	10	2.11	11.18	27.84	59.83	3.60	2.50
2	3+2	0.1	20	2.10	11.60	28.18	58.83	3.65	3.00
3	3+2	0.1	30	2.08	12.44	28.86	56.88	2.86	3.35
4	3+2	0.1	40	2.07	12.87	29.20	55.95	2.77	3.50
	Factor 2 (Cement+Dust)	Factor 3	Factor 4	Response 1	Response 2	Response 3	Response 4	Response 5	Response 6
5	3+2	0.1	50	2.06	13.29	29.55	55.03	2.65	3.85
6	3+2	0.1	60	2.06	13.29	29.55	55.03	2.50	3.85
7	3+2	0.1	70	2.05	13.71	29.89	54.14	2.48	3.85
8	3+2	0.1	80	2.05	13.71	29.89	54.14	2.40	3.80
9	3+2	0.1	90	2.04	14.13	30.23	53.27	2.40	3.90
10	3+2	0.1	95	2.03	14.55	30.57	52.41	2.35	3.95
	Cement								
11	5	0.1	10	2.12	10.76	27.49	60.86	3.79	3.50
12	5	0.1	20	2.115	10.97	27.67	60.34	4.75	3.65
13	5	0.1	30	2.110	11.18	27.84	59.83	5.82	3.73
14	5	0.1	40	2.105	11.39	28.01	59.33	6.56	3.85
15	5	0.1	50	2.105	11.60	28.18	58.83	7.10	3.90
16	5	0.1	60	2.095	11.81	28.35	58.33	7.57	3.95
17	5	0.1	70	2.090	12.02	28.52	57.84	7.30	4.00
18	5	0.1	80	2.085	12.23	28.69	57.36	7.05	4.20
19	5	0.1	90	2.080	12.44	28.86	56.88	6.37	4.22
20	5	0.1	95	2.075	12.65	29.03	56.41	5.59	4.30
21	6	0.1	10	2.125	10.55	27.32	61.39	4.65	3.00
22	6	0.1	20	2.120	10.76	27.49	60.86	5.76	3.05
23	6	0.1	30	2.115	10.97	27.67	60.34	6.12	3.17
24	6	0.1	40	2.110	11.18	27.84	59.83	6.85	3.20
25	6	0.1	50	2.105	11.39	28.01	59.33	7.31	3.40
26	6	0.1	60	2.100	11.60	28.18	58.83	7.97	3.45
27	6	0.1	70	2.095	11.81	28.35	58.33	7.25	3.50
28	6	0.1	80	2.090	12.02	28.52	57.84	6.65	3.55
29	6	0.1	90	2.085	12.23	28.69	57.36	5.96	3.65
30	6	0.1	95	2.080	12.44	28.86	56.88	4.25	3.75

It is shown that as the percentage of emulsion content increases the flow values increases, but as the percentage of cements in the filler increases the flow values reduces. This is because the emulsion particles make the samples more flexible because of high carbon content, but the cement content makes the samples more rigid because of high content of calcium and gypsum.

Table 7 showed the marshal and volumetric properties of cold mix asphalt containing different percentages of recycled asphalt pavement (RAP) from 10 to 95%, these samples were casted using optimum values of emulsion content (8%) and 0.1% of lime as re agent. It was observed

that, when 3% of cement was used as filler, only RAP of up to 20 % can be used in the mix satisfactorily, while when 5% of cement was used as filler, up to 70 % of RAP can be used in the mix satisfactorily, and when the 6% of cement was used as filler, up to 95 % of RAP can be used in the mix satisfactorily.

It was also observed that, as the percentage of RAP increased in the mix, the bulk density reduced and the voids increased, this is due to the high voids content of the RAP. Surprisingly, as the RAP increased, the flow increased, this is because of the residual bitumen content of the RAP that

was in reaction with the mix. The same pattern was observed by Pradyumna *et al.*, 2013.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The following conclusions and recommendations are found from this research:

1. Pure granites dust should not be utilized as filler for any cold mix asphalt.
2. Minimum of 3% cement can be utilized for production of cold mix recycled asphalt pavement for wearing course.
3. 8% emulsion content and 0.1% lime content should be adopted as optimum value for any cold mix recycled asphalt pavement for wearing course.
4. For utilization of RAP materials not more than 20%, 3% cement can be used as filler, while for utilization of RAP up to 70%, minimum of 5% cement must be used as filler, and finally for utilization of RAP up to 95%, minimum of 6% cement must be used as filler materials in cold mix recycled asphalt pavement.

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